

**NEW-LOOKING, MODERN, COMFORTABLE AND COMPATIBLE
CLOTHES FOR MILITARY SERVANTS OF THE ARMED FORCES OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8353124>

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Annotation : This in the article Uzbekistan Presidents Shavkat Mirziyoyev led by military in the field instead increasing wide comprehensive reforms national our army nufuzini more upgrade his _ activities time to the soul monand set off put , military servants social in support important importance profession is doing .

The key words : These aspects military servants for new in the sample military create clothing - head about practical also brilliant in efforts expression is finding .

Military headgear Create on works Tashkent textile and light industry institutes under Formal headgear design on scientific in the laboratory of the industry qualifying staff in the presence of the work take being carried out . Current kunga come

Ministry of Defense prosecutor 's office , President State security Service , State customs Committee , State security service , DXX State border security committee military servants and staff for first in the sample military clothing head and distinctive sketch of characters (attributes) projects prepared . Such wide comprehensive and very responsible function to do qualifying designers , psychologists , clothing designers , technologists , scientists and this in the direction of huge to experience has military servants and soxastaff attractive that emphasizing transition is appropriate . This direction all offer and comments , recommendations puxta , har one - sided deep analysis being done

To the analysis according to the military in the manufacture of clothing used mato and of materials normative requirements mos not the military head of clothing in size attachments in use , ergonomic indicators inobatga military __ servants jangovar clothing heads pour in providing , military wardrobe in the set some shortcomings observed that _ in the process absolutely scientific lack of approach such as cases detected . Soha experts think so _ to time until military clothing -head climate , environment , natural conditions appropriate season on separation , military activity to himself originality , hats , shoes ,

accessories tools preparation process modern requirements answer bermas was . However , the world most states , leading military structure and organizations thousands scientists , specialists , experts attractive reached without military in the manufacture of clothing wide comprehensive , structured and complex in a way approach practice available . above note reported all thought and recommendations and shortcomings inobatga received without , as well as functional issued " Road map "to basically worker group by military servants and field staff clothing heads first sketches and designs functional was released .

Created clothing heads primary samples military the first armies in units testing (approbation) , in this case field representatives , military servants , youth , people , broad of the public thought deep study , analysis offer __ and reviews summarizing , hence then military clothing heads wide in the assortment functional remove set off put designed . It is known that the military dress -head - solemn , casual (pure and from the line except) , office for , field training , special such as categories content - says Tashkent Textile _ and light industry of the institute training works on Vice Rector , Formal headgear design on scientific of the laboratory scientific leader Halida Komilova . " Military ." servants and field staff for of clothing design and sketches in preparation exactly take these into account received without structural , broad comprehensive measures instead being increased .Bunda military for clothing -head fabric , distinctive characters (attributes) , even small details quality , durability , compactness and military servants and field staff category distinctive characters , images , all-in-all firm inobatga obtained .

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